

Portable lighting customization and Light measurements NorDark Testbed, Ålesund/NW

Report

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Stockholm, March 2026

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TRITA-ABE-RPT- 2612

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All illustrations, if otherwise not mentioned: Authors

Funding: Nordforsk and Swedish Energy Agency (under NorDark Research Consortium, <https://nordark.org>)

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Acknowledgments: Ute Besenecker, Eva Persson, Seren Dincel, Georgios Tsiakiris, Lang Ning, Moa Zettergren for helping with light measurements on site and/or in the lab. All participants during the tests, and Ken Appleman and Stavroula Angelaki for review and comments.

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0. Glossary and Definition of Terms

Relevant terms based on CIE S 017/E:2020, ILV: International Lighting Vocabulary, 2nd Edition:

- **Luminance**
The measurable amount of light that is emitted or reflected from a surface in each direction, often expressed in candelas per square meter (cd/m²).
- **Illuminance**
The total amount of visible light incident on a surface per unit area, measured in lux (lx).
- **Color Temperature**
A characteristic of visible light that describes its hue as warm (yellow/red) or cool (blue), measured in Kelvin (K).
- **Glare**
Visual discomfort or reduced visibility caused by excessive brightness or contrast in a visual field.
- **Skyglow**
The brightening of the night sky overpopulated areas due to artificial lighting, contributing to light pollution.
- **Light Trespass**
Unwanted or intrusive light that spills over from one property or area to another, potentially disrupting comfort or privacy.
- **Mesopic Vision**
A combination of photopic (daylight) and scotopic (low light) vision that occurs under intermediate lighting conditions, such as dawn, dusk, or urban night scenes.
- **Photopic Vision**
Vision under well-lit conditions, primarily mediated by cone cells in the retina, enabling color perception.
- **Scotopic Vision**
Vision in low-light environments, dominated by rod cells, with limited color discrimination and reduced visual acuity.
- **Spectral Power Distribution (SPD)**
A graph or data set that shows the power emitted by a light source at each wavelength across the visible spectrum.

- **Uniformity Ratio**
A measure of the consistency of lighting across a surface, calculated as the ratio of minimum to average or maximum illuminance.
- **Adaptation (Visual)**
The process by which the human visual system adjusts to changes in lighting levels, allowing effective perception across a wide range of brightness.
- **Color Rendering Index (CRI)**
A quantitative measure of a light source's ability to reveal the true colors of objects compared to natural light.
- **Glare Disability Glare, Discomfort Glare**
- **Light Pollution**
Any adverse effect of artificial light on the natural environment, including glare, skyglow, and light trespass.
- **Luminous Flux**
The total amount of visible light emitted by a source, measured in lumens (lm).

1. Introduction

1.1. Project and Site Context

This technical report details the methodologies and summarizes the results obtained from measurements of illuminance and luminance levels as well as spectral qualities conducted in Lerstadvatnet, *Ålesund*, Norway, during specified days and time periods between November 2023 and November 2024. This report is part of the interdisciplinary research initiative, NorDark, a project that brings relevant disciplines together to explore wildlife-aware lighting with representatives from design, technology, psychology and ecology. The NorDark consortium includes 6 universities from Sweden, Norway and Finland as well the industry partner *Tyréns* covering different research fields and working on dedicated work packages (WPs). The NorDark research consortium consists of: WP1: Environmental Psychology, Lund University; WP2: Stress Physiology, Stockholm University; WP3: Wildlife Ecology, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences; WP4: Lighting Design, KTH Royal Institute of Technology; WP5: Digital Technology, Norwegian University of Science and Technology; and WP6: Sustainable Futures, Aalto University (reference NorDark page). Since there is a school located near the path, some of the teachers and students' parents mentioned the need to have light (during the dark hours/seasons) in the site where we did the studies.

Overall, the NorDark research consortium strives to develop new knowledge crucial to design for sustainability in the urban after-dark. In order to develop in a sustainable way, we need to balance our needs with the needs of nature. In this broader context, one focus area particularly relevant in Nordic countries is the use of electric light in after-dark outdoor environments, and the impact it has on flora, fauna, and energy use, as well as human behavior and wellbeing. All research teams within the NorDark consortium conduct field studies and monitoring activities at two designated project sites, Uppsala, Sweden, and *Ålesund*, Norway, during the dark season.

This report outlines the process of defining the *Ålesund* project site, selecting locations for light measurements, using a measurement protocol previously developed by other Nordark team member, Seren Dincel, and summarizing empirical data. The initial section of the technical report focuses on light measurements at both horizontal ground level and vertical eye level followed by the characterization and development of a portable lighting option for pedestrian users of the walking paths. The collection and management of the light measurement data were conducted by

WP4: Lighting Design research group from KTH. The site for the light measurements and related study was established through collaborative discussions with the municipality and the other research teams within the NorDark consortium. The length of the pathway and the specific sites along the walking route at Lerstadvatnet, Ålesund, were particularly critical for WP1: Environmental Psychology, LTH, and WP4: Lighting Design, KTH. These work packages required the site for their field studies, which involved conducting walks with research participants and performing light measurements. Following consultations with the respective teams, a segment of approximately 200 meters along the walking path was identified and designated for field studies (Fig. 1). In addition, WP6 and WP4 worked with teachers and pupils from the adjacent school to discuss local nature and ecology concerns, and WP5 designed a digital version of the site for analysis and representation.

Figure 1. The project location in Ålesund and chosen part of path for the field studies.

Figure 2. The only light pole in the chosen path, located on Grid 1. Source: Google Maps.

The chosen path has only one light pole in the beginning (Fig.2) and no other light installed along the path to the end of selected path (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Photos from the Grid 2 (middle point of the path).

In addition to characterizing lighting on the site, WP4 purchased and adjusted pedestrian headlamps as part of the NorDark project to facilitate the testing of portable lighting solutions when walking the site in Lerstad, Ålesund. The development and characterization of portable lighting is also part of this report.

1.2. Existing Lighting Conditions

1.2.1. Light measurement grid for existing conditions

In order to better understand the existing lighting conditions, a simple light measurement grid was developed to be used for two rounds of light measurements for both daytime and after dark. The measurement grid was informed by the Illuminating Engineering Society's (IES) standards and the dialogues between NorDark consortium partners and defined by one of the NorDark members (S. Dincel), see Fig. 4 for measurement grid. In addition to the pathway measurements, for grid location 2, measurement points were included 4 m towards the sides (F1-F6). The measurement points on the pathway were coded as "P" and the ones outside of the pathway were coded as "F". At each

Figure 4. The measurement grid between the area of pole positions 1-2 is developed for both light measurements for NorDark research project in Ålesund.- Grid drawings: Seren Dincel.

measurement point, the light level was measured horizontal on ground level (facing up) and vertical at eye level (facing the walking direction), at 1.50 meters height. Within the path (P points), for vertical measurements, device was directed towards the end of the path and for "F" measurements as a part of Grid 2, directed towards the path.

Illuminance (lux) and luminance (cd/m^2) as well as spectral measurements on site were collected by using several devices during the measurements (Fig. 5):

- A. Luminance camera LMK Mobile Air, used for taking HDR images
- B. Iphone 13 mini, used for capturing photos
- C. Luminance meter Konica Minolta for checking reference luminance points
- D. Spectrometer GL Spectis touch 1.0+SALLI, used for nighttime illuminance measurements
- E. Spectrometer GL Spectis 1.0 touch, used for daytime measurement of illuminance and CCT

Figure 5. Different measurement and capturing devices used on site and during the development tests.

In addition to the yearly factory calibration of the light measurement devices, frequent site calibrations were performed during the on-site measurements to accommodate outdoor temperature changes.

1.2.2. Light measurement outcomes

Below is a summary of the measurements taken on site during two different years. Additional information can be found in the appendix.

Measurement Round I – 18 October 2023: The first light measurements were collected on 18th October 2023. Measurements were taken during the day under a clear sky and partly cloudy conditions during the nighttime measurements. On this day, sunrise was at 08:28 and sunset was 18:11. On October 18, 2023, in Ålesund, Norway, the moon was in its waxing crescent phase, with approximately 16% of its surface illuminated. During this phase, the moon becomes visible in the western sky after sunset, with the right edge illuminated as it progresses toward the first quarter. Daytime light measurements were collected between 11:27–12:15 and evening measurements between 19:50–20:39. The highest daytime light level was 15164 lux and the lowest was 2761 lux. The CCT ranged from 5700–6600 K. The highest evening light level was 7,82 lux (grid 1 where some electric lighting was installed) while the lowest was 0,01 lux (grid 2 where no electric lighting was installed near the path), as illustrated in Appendix 1. Due to low levels of lights at night, no CCT measurements were taken.

Measurement Round II – 25 October 2024: The second field work of light measurements was conducted on 25th October 2024. Measurements were taken during cloudy sky conditions for daytime and an overcast sky for the evening. For this day, sunrise was at 08:49, and sunset was at 17:48. The moon was in its waning crescent phase, with approximately 34% of its surface illuminated. Daytime light measurements were collected between 11:00 –11:29; and evening measurements occurred between 19:50–20:50. The highest daytime light level measured was 7197 lux and the lowest was 1582 lux. The CCT ranged from 5200–6500 K. The highest light level for the evening measurements was 7,71 lux (grid 1 where some electric lighting was installed) while the lowest was 0.01 lux (grid 2 where no electric lighting was installed near the path), as illustrated in Appendix 1. Due to low levels of lights at night, no CCT measurements were taken.

2. Background

2.1. Reflections on outdoor lighting strategies

The human need for illumination after dark has historically led to a wide array of lighting solutions—from open flame torches and oil lamps to different luminaires using initially incandescent and now LED light sources. While the function of these sources has remained consistent (to provide visibility in darkness), the form and environmental impact have changed over time (Fig. 6). Initially, lighting was portable and utilitarian, illuminating only the immediate surroundings. The introduction of fixed public lighting, first with gas lamps and later with electric streetlights, marked a pivotal transition toward broad, static illumination of entire pathways and urban environments (Longcore & Rich, 2004).

This transition, while beneficial for visibility and safety, has introduced unintended consequences such as light pollution, defined as excessive or misdirected artificial light that

Figure 6. Outdoor lighting strategies.

disrupts natural darkness (Falchi et al., 2016). Currently, over 80% of the global population lives under light-polluted skies, with nearly 99% of the population in Europe and North America being affected (Falchi et al., 2016). These shifts have occurred relatively recently in human history, prompting concerns about how modern lighting affects both ecological systems and human health.

In recent decades, growing attention has been paid to the ecological consequences of artificial lighting. Wildlife species have evolved in sync with natural light cycles, and

disruptions to these rhythms can have profound consequences. Artificial light at night (ALAN) has been shown to interfere with nocturnal animals' movement patterns, foraging behavior, predator-prey relationships, and reproductive cycles (Gaston et al., 2013; Longcore & Rich, 2004). Particularly sensitive are amphibians, birds, and insects, many of which rely on natural darkness for orientation and mating rituals (Pawson & Bader, 2014).

The spectral composition of light is a critical factor. Short wavelength "blue" light, typical of many white LEDs, has been found to be especially disruptive to both wildlife and human circadian rhythms. Conversely, long-wavelength lighting, such as amber or red light, is assumed to come with a reduced ecological footprint when compared to white light (Holker et al., 2010). Therefore, sustainable lighting strategies often involve minimizing blue-rich light in favor of warmer tones that are likely less intrusive to ecosystems.

Artificial light can impact human health and perception in multiple ways. Excessive exposure to bright or poorly directed lighting can lead to glare (discomfort, and reduced visibility), especially in natural, otherwise unlit environments (Rea et al., 2010). High-intensity headlamps, for example, can cause visual discomfort for both the wearer and approaching individuals, and impairing night vision by creating stark contrasts between lit and unlit areas (Schlyter, 2012).

Furthermore, prolonged exposure to light at night has been linked to sleep disorders, increased stress, and melatonin suppression in humans (Chepesiuk, 2009). These effects are more pronounced when lighting includes higher amounts of short wavelengths, which interfere with the body's circadian regulation (Stevens et al., 2013). Thus, from both a physiological and perceptual standpoint, both light quality and quantity are critical components to be addressed in outdoor lighting design.

In Nordic countries, the widespread use of headlamps and portable lighting devices reflects a cultural adaptation to the region's long periods of darkness, especially in winter. Outdoor activities such as running, skiing, and dog walking are common after sunset which in winter occurs during daytime hours, necessitating individual light sources due to the lack of fixed lighting infrastructure in many forested or preserved areas (NordForsk, 2024). The cultural value of *friluftsliv* (outdoor life) encourages year-round outdoor activity, increasing reliance on personal lighting for safety and navigation.

However, this reliance comes with environmental and social trade-offs. High-intensity headlamps can potentially disorient nocturnal wildlife, contribute to localized light pollution,

and cause discomfort to other users sharing the path (Fristrup et al., 2024). In rural and urban forests—where no pole lights are installed along most trails—residents routinely use personal lighting, making it an ideal test case for low-impact lighting design.

This report addresses such a site, the *Lerstad* residential neighborhood in the City of *Ålesund*, Norway, adjacent to a nature preserve.

2.2. Project Motivation and Scope

Developing a customized headlamp as a part of the Nordark project started after deciding to test portable instead of fixed-installed light solution at the site in *Ålesund*, Norway. The selection of the location was established through collaborative discussions with the *Ålesund* municipality and other research teams within the NorDark research consortium (Fig. 7).

This report seeks to address the environmental and ergonomic challenges associated with personal headlamp use in outdoor environments, particularly nature preserves adjacent to residential neighborhoods. Motivated by the observed use of personal, carried lighting and the challenges of fixed-installed lighting infrastructure in protected nature areas, the design team of the NorDark consortium explored in *Ålesund* the use of headlamps as sustainable, more than human-centric lighting solution.

By exploring adjustments to portable head torch lighting qualities, such as reduced light intensity, warmer color appearance of the light, and modified optical distribution, the goal was to develop a headlamp that provides sufficient visibility for users to walk comfortably on pathways in urban forests while minimizing disruption to wildlife, creation of light pollution, and glare. This approach aligns with current best practices in sustainable lighting design, which emphasize minimal intervention, context sensitivity, and ecosystem health in outdoor environments. (International Dark-Sky Association, 2022).

Figure 7. Photos from the site during evening in winter in *Ålesund*.

2.3. Background Literature and Standards

At the onset of the project, standards guidance for outdoor illumination were consulted, comparing European (EN 13201), Swedish (TRVINFRA-00395) and Norwegian (Håndbok V124) Standards relevant for sites such as the one described here in *Ålesund*.

Lighting classes for walkways are defined in six different P-classes according to Norwegian, Swedish and European standards. The class indicating the lowest light level, P6, 2 lux in average value on ground is the one that best corresponds to the illumination levels appropriate for the chosen site if lighting were to be installed. According to the standard, there are also classes for vertical illuminance, when necessary, with a minimum value of 0.6 lux according to the Norwegian and European standard and 0.5 lux in Swedish standards. It should be noted that in the Swedish standard, the guidelines for vertical illuminance have been separated from the guidelines for horizontal illumination of walkways. Vertical illuminance requirements only apply where specific vertical illuminance needs are required, such as at pedestrian crossings. As illustrated in later chapters, headlamps can provide such light levels in front of a person walking, however, naturally, illumination from headlamps cannot provide the same uniformity of average illuminance level over the length and width of a path as traditional pole-mounted lighting. (See appendices part 8.3 – tables of standards)

In the latest version of “the Swedish Requirement TRVINFRA-00395 Design of Roads and Streets” a new chapter has been added, 13.1.1 Light pollution. This chapter sets out several requirements for lighting design in order to reduce light pollution and contribute to a better light-dark environment for humans, animals and nature. Examples of new requirements include the CCT of light sources that should not exceed 3000K, and a maximum ratio for up-lighting from luminaires as well as requirements to limit lighting outside of urban areas and that demand-oriented controls should be used.

3. Methods

In addition to the site measurements reported in the introduction, several measurements related to the portable headlamp testing and customization were taken in lab environments, including the lighting lab at the Swedish Energy Agency and at the KTH Lighting laboratory in Stockholm, Sweden.

3.1. Testing process

To assess the off-the-shelf headlamp and develop a customization, five steps were carried out in spring and fall 2024 to test and develop an alternate version:

(1) Check for position of light on the body (usability), (2) tilt of the source (focus on path and glare reduction), (3) CCT (color appearance of the light), (4) optical distribution (limiting spread into periphery), (5) outdoor pilot testing (acceptability for users)

3.1.2 Location of tests

All tests except the “outdoor pilot test” were performed in the Black Lab at KTH Lighting lab (Fig. 8). The black lab is a controlled room with matt black finishings on ceiling, floor and walls with no access to daylight to be able to mimic total dark conditions. The “outdoor pilot test” was conducted along a footpath in the forest area “Lill-Jansskogen” near KTH Campus, Stockholm.

Figure 8. Testing in the Black Lab at KTH Lighting Lab.

3.2 Analysis and development

During the lab and field testing, measurements and related analyses were carried out through visual assessment by the research team consisting of experienced lighting design professionals. In addition, documentation (see reference list) was consulted as a basis for decision making on further development of the portable light.

4. Development of headlamp customization

During steps (1) and (2) the headlamp used for on-site testing in *Ålesund* in the fall of 2023 was used as basis and placed in five different positions on a test person.

After a review, the research team decided that mounting the light on the head was the best position for visibility, especially when the light was angled 45 degrees downward to the ground. Angling the luminaire down 45 degrees also helped to reduce glare towards oncoming people. Wearing the light on the forehead enables us to have the hands free and moving the light just by moving the head.

Scientific studies show that it is the amount of light, its distribution and spectrum that can have a negative impact on many animal species (Gaston & Holt-Laursen et al. 2022). In developing a customized headlamp prototype, the research team, therefore, aimed at lowering short wavelength light content and overall light output within a user acceptable range that needed to be tested. According to several studies, long wavelength radiation (orange and red appearing light) is less invasive to many species than short wavelength (blue appearing light).

During step (3) the team tested several different color filters filtering out short wavelength radiation. Using color filters on the headlamp also reduced and dimmed the overall amount of light from the light source. The filter LEE Half Orange 205, a light filter line used predominantly in entertainment lighting, was selected for its transmission properties; it transformed the white-appearing light of the original headlamp (CCT7590) into amber-appearing light (CCT 2803K). During step (5), when pedestrians walked outdoors along a forest footpath, the test persons used two types of filtered headlamps: LEE Half Orange 205, and LEE Golden Amber 134, with cut-out slit.

As a result of these walks, the Half Orange 205 filter was selected to be used for the final prototype.

In step (4), different optics were assessed to minimize light where it is not needed and to optimize the function for the user of the headlamp. The team assessed the original off-the-shelf headlamp which had a symmetric light pattern of 60° beam spread, in addition to several different off-the shelf optical alternatives to evaluate effects on visibility and glare. The criteria for the optics were to be asymmetrical, close to 25° beam spread horizontally and 40° vertically. A smooth fall-off was preferred over a harsh cut-off.

After visual tests, the optic selected was CA14392_LXP2-O-WAS by Ledil with an asymmetric optics of 15° vertical and 8° horizontal and with some degree of surrounding light. The narrow horizontal optics enabled a reduction of glare towards the viewer. (See appendix part 4).

4.1. Steps (1) and (2): Positioning and tilt

To determine where on the body portable light is best placed, tests were carried out in March 2024 in the KTH Lighting lab. The headlamp (used for on-site testing in Ålesund) was used and placed in five different positions on a test person: S1 Head 0, S1 Head 45, S2 Chest, S3 Hand, S4 Belt, S5 Leg above knee, see Figures 9-11.

Figure 9. illustration of different placement of headlamp in the positioning test.

For each condition, illuminance and luminance measurements were taken in the dark room at two different distances, 5m and 2.5m from the test person at a height of 1.5m vertically towards the test person.

Figure 10. Left: Photos from positioning tests. Right: illustration of Headlamp with 0-degree (a) and with a 45-degree tilt downward (b).

Luminance levels (cd/m ²) measured towards the light source			
	Position	5m	2.5m
S1 0°	Head	1400	4500
S1 45°	Head	2100	4800
S2	Chest	4600	8600
S3	Hand	1500	3300
S4	Belt	1700	5500
S5	Leg (Knee)	500	1030

Figure 11. Table of different luminance levels measured for each position. Luminance measured in direction of the light source

The chest and belt positions produced higher luminance levels (more glare potential) for an oncoming person and produced a compromised angle of light distribution for the wearer to get good lighting conditions on the ground. Hand and leg mounted conditions produced less glare for the viewer, but the moving light created visual difficulties both for the user and viewer (approaching person).

All conditions that had the light placed lower than the head could not provide illumination on the face of the wearer; this is relevant because an illuminated, recognizable face increases the perceived safety for approaching people (Boyce, Rea, & Peter, 1990).

Vertical illumination at face height ensures visibility of facial features. Whilst mean horizontal illuminance is the core metric, adding vertical or semi-cylindrical levels enhances interpersonal visual tasks.

4.2 Step 3: CCT and color filters tests

As described above, the aim was to minimize short wavelength output of the lamp, while supporting visual comfort and performance. The following process was used to select the spectrum for the modified headlamp.

Several different color filters were selected from the company LEE: Dark Amber 022, Full Orange 204, Half Orange 205, Primary Red 106 to visually test a variety of configurations. Filters were cut and placed on the top of the optics under the rim. (Fig. 12).

Additionally, in the darkroom, luminance measurements were taken at two different distances, 5m and 2.5m from the test person and at a height of 1.5m vertically towards the test person to assess the light reduction and dimming effect of the filter (Fig. 13 and 14).

Figure 12. Images from color test using LEE filters.

Figure 13. Photos taken during the comparison tests of different color filters on headlamp in the Darkroom.

Measured luminance levels (Cd/m ²) using different color filters when the device were facing towards the light source		
Color/Distance	5 m	2.5 m
Redish 022 dark amber	520	1128
Half orange 205	320	1071
Full orange 204	350	1400
Primary red 106	24	95

Figure 14. Measured luminance levels (Cd/m²) using different color filters.

The research team assessed that the filters 022 and 106 removed more than 70 and 80 percent of light for their visibility needed and skewed the color too much towards a saturated red to recognize colors well enough. 204 also removed more than 60 percent of light and resulted in a slightly green glow. Filter 205 had a higher transmission in combination with a reasonable amber light color. After an additional on-site field-test (step 5), 205 was the one selected for customization.

4.3. Step 4: Optics and distribution tests

To minimize light where it is not needed to recognize the path, different optics were tested. The original, off-the-shelf headlamp used in *Ålesund* had a symmetric light pattern of 60°. Different products and optics were ordered to evaluate how they would affect visibility for the user and glare for an oncoming person. In addition, glare shields such as honeycomb lenses and caps were tested.

All tests were performed in the Black lab at KTH and were assessed based on visual evaluation by the research team. In summary, the following was observed:

- The off-the-shelf headlamp has a symmetric lens optic at 60° which appeared too wide both in the vertical and horizontal axis.
- Aim to reduce/narrow horizontal light angle and light towards the sides with a smooth fall-off.
- Aim to keep a relatively wide vertical light distribution to throw light along the path, while focusing on the ground and reducing glare for oncoming walkers.
- Louvers and caps provided some glare reduction but also restricted view for user and would need to be developed in ways beyond the scope of this project.

As a result of in-house explorations, the target angles were set at asymmetric 25° horizontally and 40° vertically, and five respective optics were ordered for assessment from LEDIL.

The following LEDIL optics were ordered: CA 11267_HEIDI-O-90, CA 14197_HEIDI-REC-90, CP 12415_LOS-O-90, CA14392_LXP2-O-WAS, and CA13307_LAURA-O-WAS-PIN (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Image from headlamps with replaced lenses for testing

The research team considered light distribution to be more on the path and less on the peripheral as well as choosing the one with lower glare mostly in the dark room both visual with use of comparing images of lights. During the evaluation, using the head lamp to see the

path and the approaching person as well as considering the glare for the other pedestrians was visually evaluated. The optic that was evaluated the best for both the user and the observer was CA14392_LXP2-O-WAS. It has an asymmetric optics of 15° vertical and 8° horizontal and with some degree of slush/spill light. To the authors' surprise, narrower optics than anticipated felt more appropriate than wider ones. Having narrow horizontal optics was a good way to reduce glare towards the viewer and reduce peripheral lighting beyond the path.

4.4. Step 5: On site test (pilot)

After optics and configurations were selected, a pilot assessment was carried out in a forested area close to the KTH campus with pedestrian participants walking along a forest footpath similar to the test site in *Ålesund*. 5 participants (2 female, 3 male, ages 20-35), all students at KTH, participated in the pilot assessment, one by one, to inform the selection of the headlamp configuration.

The participants were asked to test two types of headlamps. Both headlamps had the selected asymmetric optic, but different color filters, Option 1 used LEE Half Orange 205 (transmittance 70%), Option 2 used LEE Golden Amber 134 (transmittance 34%) with a cut-out slit in the center to test whether light can be further reduced in the periphery if unfiltered, white light in the center of the light beam would support the visual performance of the participants (Fig. 16).

Figure 16. Images showing two prototypes used for the pilot test.

Participants were asked to meet at the starting point of a path; the participant was given the respective headlamp (Option 1 or 2) to wear by a researcher and was instructed to walk for about 5 minutes on the otherwise unlit path in a wooded area. In the middle of the path, a second researcher was positioned to instruct the participant to fill out a questionnaire while being surrounded by the forest before continuing the walk. At the end of the path a third researcher welcomed the participant and asked them to fill in a final set of questions and comments before walking back using an illuminated alternative path. Each participant did the walk twice with the two different headlamp options; the order was alternated between participants (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Selected path for the headlamp selection test behind the KTH main campus. Source: Google maps.

Figure 18. Photos from the pilot test.

The below two diagrams (Fig. 19-20) summarize the averaged outcomes from the participants' questionnaire responses:

Figure 19. Average lighting perceived qualities perceived by the 5 participants.

Figure 20. Average visibility and comfort perceived by the 5 participants.

experience of walking in dark rural environments and the familiarity with the surroundings will likely affect feelings of safety and comfort.

We also asked an additional participant, age above 60, to also walk the path with both headlamps. Both headlamps were evaluated several points lower in visibility, with Option 1 being rated overall higher for providing visibility.

While this survey did not have enough participants for generalizable results or statistical analysis, participant ratings were largely consistent. The results indicated that ratings for Option 1 and Option 2 were close, less than one. Generally, Option 1 was rated slightly glarier and cooler in light color appearance, but also higher to see surrounding details. One participant mentioned that would not consider using Option 2, only Option 1, while other participants mentioned that they would use both products. Generally, however, Option 1 was mentioned in open comments as providing better visibility of surroundings. This pilot was used to inform the choice for the headlamp configuration used for evaluations at the Ålesund site. It has to be noted that prior

5. Summary comparison of two headlamps (off-the shelf and customized)

5.1 Lab measurements of original headlamp

To be able to compare the technical performance of the original headlamp with the prototype headlamp, measurements were carried out in February 2025 in KTH's Black lab. The headlamp used for on-site testing in Ålesund in the fall of 2023 was used and placed on a tripod on a height of 1.6m. Measurements were taken at two different distances, 5m and 2.5m from the tripod and at a height of 1.5m for the measuring tool. Measures were taken, if possible, horizontally on the ground and vertically from a height of 1.5m. From the two distances

Figure 21. Cross section drawing of measurement setup for luminance measurement mode: Towards the path.

Figure 22. Cross section drawing of measurement setup for luminance measurement mode: Towards the light.

measurements were taken both towards the headlamp and with the Headlamp placed beside the measuring position (Fig. 21 and 22).

Luminance levels / Luminance meter (cd/m ²)					
	Towards the light		Facing the path		
Distance	2.5m	5m	2.5m	5m	
Direction	H	V	H	H	V
Original	0.26	7416	0.02	0.06	2.57
Prototype	2.8	293	0.1	0.005	0.019

Figure 23. Table of Luminance levels measured using luminance meter towards the light and towards the path. H: Horizontal on the ground and V: Vertical.

Luminance, Luminance camera

Similarly a series of measurements were taken using HDR Luminance camera (Mobile Air + LMK Software) to get the average luminance values in the same setting (Fig. 22 and 23).

Below (Fig. 24) are the results from the LMK software:

LMK Luminance pictures analysis / Luminance averages (cd/m ²)				
	Towards the light		Towards the path	
Distance	2.5m	5m	2.5m	5m
Original	24	4325	-	12.8
Prototype	86.5	350	-	14.3

Figure 24. Average luminance values from LMK software measured towards the light and towards the path using Mobile Air HDR camera.

Figure 25. Cross section drawing of measurement setup for luminance HDR measurement mode: Towards the path.

Figure 26. Cross section drawing of measurement setup for luminance HDR measurement mode: Towards the light.

The headlamp used for on-site testing in Ålesund in the fall of 2023 was used and placed on a tripod on a height of 1.6m. Measurements were made at two different distances, 5m and 2.5m from the tripod and at a height of 1.5m for the measuring tool. Measures were taken horizontally on the ground and vertically from a height of 1.5m. Measurements were made with the headlamp placed beside the measuring position for measures done for:

Illuminance, Spectrometer

A GL Optic touch 1.0 device were used to measure the illuminance levels made by the original and prototyped (customized) headlamp in different distances of 2.5m and 5m both on the ground and vertically at 1.5 m (Fig. 27). Measurements were made in the same way as for the original headlamp, se 5.1.

Illuminance levels - lux				
Distance	2.5 m		5 m	
Direction	H	V	H	V
Original	13.9 Lux	46.91 Lux	0.97	16.87
Prototype	3.78 Lux	0.91 Lux	0.50	0.60

Figure 27. Table of illuminance levels made by the original and Prototyped headlamps.

Figure 28. Images showing the original headlamp (Top) and the Prototype headlamp (bottom)

5.2 Software simulation/Calculations

Figure 29. Light distribution pattern (Dialux evo simulation) and measured spectral power distribution (SPD) showing the relative output in the visible range from the off-the-shelf, regular headtorch (left), and customized, modified head torch (right)

Since there was a demand for having 6-8 identical headlamps to be used during the actual walks for data collection in Norway, we made a binning process visually, and then by using a spectrometer, to find the same LED chipsets in terms of light characteristics such as luminous flux and CCT.

5.3 Comparison of two options

Lighting			Aiming and distribution	Correlated color temperature (CCT) in Kelvin	Light Output from Source in Lumen	Horizontal Illuminance at 2.5m distance on ground in Lux	Vertical Illuminance at 2.5m distance, 1.5 m height in Lux
October daylight, overcast or partly cloudy sky condition			Immersive,	5200 – 6900	NA	2600 – 21000	700 – 8600
Off-the-shelf (regular)		Straight, with wide	7590 (cool-white)	39	14*	47*	
Customized head torch		Tilted 45°, with	2803 (warm-white)	7	4*	1*	

Figure 30. Table showing summary of lighting conditions used during the walks: October daylight, after-dark use of off-the-shelf head torch used in the first round of walks and customized head torch used in the second round of walks. Both head torch versions complied with general recommendations for rendering surface colors. (* Light level measured 0.01-0.02 lux without use of any head torch).

6. Discussion, considerations and limitations

The fact that we chose to start with the original headlamp and to modify it was based on several limitations, including budget, timing and making sure that it is one of the most affordable options for the users in the market.

The study has been limited to the items mentioned, and the following factors have not been taken into consideration:

1. The quality of the LED; CRI, McAdam
2. Color temperature of the LED
3. Brightness of the LED and that it could not be dimmed
4. Limitation in the type of lenses that could be mounted in the luminaire

Each needs further investigations and research that could be done in future studies.

7. References

- Boyce, P. R., Rea, M. S., & Peter, R. (1990). Security lighting: Effects of illuminance and light source on the capabilities of guards and intruders. *Lighting Research and Technology*, 22(2), 57–79. <https://doi.org/10.1177/096032719002200201>
- Chepesiuk, R. (2009). Missing the dark: Health effects of light pollution. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 117(1), A20–A27. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.117-a20>
- European Committee for Standardization. (2018). EN 12193:2018 Sports lighting. CEN.
- European Committee for Standardization. (2014). EN 12464-1:2014 Lighting of outdoor workplaces. CEN.
- European Committee for Standardization. (n.d.). EN 13201 Road lighting (various parts). CEN.
- Falchi, F., Cinzano, P., Duriscoe, D., Kyba, C. C. M., Elvidge, C. D., Baugh, K., ... Furgoni, R. (2016). The new world atlas of artificial night sky brightness. *Science Advances*, 2(6), e1600377. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1600377>
- Fristrup, K., Miller, Z. D., Newton, J., Buckley, S., Cole, H., Linares, C., ... Newman, P. (2024). National park visitors perceive benefits for themselves and wildlife under blended red-white outdoor lighting. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 21791. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-71868-4>
- Gaston, K. J., Visser, M. E., & Hölker, F. (2013). The biological impacts of artificial light at night: The research challenge. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 370(1667), 20140133. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2014.0133>
- Hölker, F., Wolter, C., Perkin, E. K., & Tockner, K. (2010). Light pollution as a biodiversity threat. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 25(12), 681–682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2010.09.007>
- International Commission on Illumination. (1997). CIE 126-1997 Guidelines for minimising sky glow. CIE.
- International Commission on Illumination. (1998). CIE 129-1998 Guide to the lighting of exterior working areas. CIE.
- International Commission on Illumination. (2003). CIE 150-2003 Guide on the limitation of the effects of obtrusive light from outdoor lighting installations. CIE.
- International Commission on Illumination. (2017). CIE 150 (2nd ed.) Guide on the limitation of the effects of obtrusive light from outdoor lighting installations. CIE.
- International Dark-Sky Association. (2022). Principles for responsible outdoor lighting. <https://www.darksky.org/our-work/lighting/lighting-for-citizens/lighting-basics/>

- ISO/CIE. (2018). ISO/CIE 8995-3:2018 Lighting of workplaces — Part 3: Lighting requirements for safety and security of outdoor workplaces. ISO & CIE.
- LightingEurope. (2025, June). Guidance and information paper on the use of lighting product standards in Europe. LightingEurope.
- Longcore, T., & Rich, C. (2004). Ecological light pollution. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 2(4), 191–198. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2004\)002\[0191:ELP\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2004)002[0191:ELP]2.0.CO;2)
- NordForsk. (2024). How much path lighting do we really need in urban green areas? Researchers try to give an answer. <https://www.nordforsk.org/news/how-much-path-lighting-do-we-really-need-urban-green-areas-researchers-try-give-answer>
- Pawson, S. M., & Bader, M. K.-F. (2014). LED lighting increases the ecological impact of light pollution irrespective of color temperature. *Ecological Applications*, 24(7), 1561–1568. <https://doi.org/10.1890/13-1330.1>
- Rea, M. S., Bullough, J. D., Akashi, Y., & Figueiro, M. G. (2010). A model of visual performance for outdoor lighting. *Lighting Research & Technology*, 42(2), 215–232. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477153509359630>
- Schlyter, P. (2012). Effects of light pollution on human health, wildlife, and climate. Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, Environmental Advisory Council.
- Statens vegvesen. (n.d.). HB V124: Handbok – vägars och gaturs utformning (pp. 441 [503]).
- Stevens, R. G., Brainard, G. C., Blask, D. E., Lockley, S. W., & Motta, M. E. (2013). Adverse health effects of nighttime lighting: Comments on American Medical Association policy statement. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 45(3), 343–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2013.04.010>
- Transportetat Norge. (n.d.). Krav TRVINFRA-00396 Vägers och gaturs utformning v1_0 (p. 15).

8. Appendices

8.1. Site Measurements

Illustration: Grid of ground level measurements

Daytime

Round 1

Evening

Round 1

Round 2

Round 2

Tables showing Values of ground level measurements

Round 1, Daytime, Grid 1, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)				
Position No.	Illuminance (lux)	Color temp. (K)	Peak wavelength (nm)	S/P ratio
P1	6742	6067	477	0,97
P2	7394	6177	462	0,97
P3	8570	6261	462	0,98
P4	5124	6514	462	1,00
P5	7470	6075	477	0,97
P6	8576	6128	477	0,97
P7	8757	6219	477	0,98
P8	6377	5720	477	0,94
P9	9062	5910	477	0,95
P10	8682	6068	477	0,97
P11	6698	5909	477	0,95
P12	6931	6042	477	0,96
P13	7014	6307	462	0,98
P14	6043	6156	477	0,97
P15	6600	6278	462	0,98

Round 1, Daytime, Grid 2, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)				
Position No.	Illuminance (lux)	Color temp. (K)	Peak wavelength (nm)	S/P ratio
P16	8190	6400	460	0,99
P17	8552	6419	462	0,99
P18	6622	6558	460	1,00
P19	9425	6462	462	0,99
P20	8622	6506	460	1,00
P21	6958	6548	462	1,00
P22	10298	6394	462	0,99
P23	10192	6364	462	0,99
P24	9060	6434	460	0,99
P25	11045	6374	462	0,99
P26	10736	6404	460	0,99
P27	10212	6463	462	0,99
P28	9538	6130	477	0,97
P29	10934	6367	460	0,99
P30	10940	6360	462	0,99

F01	9421	6065	477	0,96
F02	12458	5972	477	0,96
F03	15164	5934	477	0,96
F04	2761	5954	778	0,94
F05	8174	6068	477	0,96
F06	10868	6241	462	0,98

Round 2, Daytime, Grid 1, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)				
Position No.	Illuminance (lux)	CCT (K)	Peak wavelength (nm)	S/P ratio
P1	4802	5527	496	0.92
P2	6061	5412	535	0.91
P3	3588	5383	535	0.91
P4	6999	5248	535	0.90
P5	7197	5324	535	0.91
P6	5381	5606	494	0.93
P7	4909	5322	535	0.90
P8	5996	5321	535	0.90
P9	6039	5357	535	0.91
P10	4808	5304	535	0.90
P11	5440	5377	535	0.91
P12	3659	5639	496	0.93
P13	2306	5798	479	0.94
P14	2689	5701	494	0.94
P15	2687	5830	479	0.95

Round 2, Daytime, Grid 2, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)				
Position No.	Illuminance (lux)	Color temp. (K)	Peak wavelength (nm)	S/P ratio
P16	4179	6013	479	0.96
P17	3782	6208	479	0.98
P18	3208	6118	479	0.97
P19	3518	6446	461	0.99
P20	3359	6383	461	0.99
P21	2535	6359	461	0.99
P22	3552	6104	479	0.97
P23	3469	6124	479	0.97
P24	3249	6030	479	0.96

P25	3815	5984	479	0.96
P26	3970	5986	479	0.96
P27	3815	5991	479	0.96
P28	4888	5570	494	0.93
P29	4355	5694	479	0.94
P30	3884	5744	479	0.94
F01	4179	5993	479	0.96
F02	4505	5684	494	0.94
F03	4959	5661	494	0.93
F04	1582	5720	778	0.94
F05	1727	5894	748	0.95
F06	2286	5986	479	0.96

Round 1, Evening, Grid 1, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)	
Position No.	Illuminance (lux)
P1	6,91
P2	7,82
P3	7,58
P4	7,09
P5	5,67
P6	5,51
P7	5,09
P8	2,46
P9	3,11
P10	3,30
P11	1,28
P12 (shadow of a person)	0,43
P13	1,10
P14	0,098
P15	0,58

Round 1, Evening, Grid 2, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)	
Position No.	Illuminance (lux)
P16	0,0080
P17	0,0060
P18	0,0160
P19	0,0190

P20	0,0076
P21	0,0140
P22	0,0160
P23	0,0077
P24	0,0150
P25	0,0150
P26	0,0092
P27	0,0110
P28	0,0180
P29	0,0170
P30	0,0150

Round 2, Evening, Grid 1, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)

Position No.	Illuminance (lux)
P1	7.71
P2	7.65
P3	7.47
P4	5.96
P5	5.98
P6	5.23
P7	2.49
P8	2.96
P9	3.17
P10	1.40
P11	1.67
P12	1.25
P13	0.14
P14	0.39
P15	0.70

Round 2, Evening, Grid 2, Ground level (h: 0.00 m)

Position No.	Illuminance (lux)
P16	0.022
P17	0.029
P18	0.029
P19	0.022
P20	0.027

P21	0.019
P22	0.019
P23	0.032
P24	0.022
P25	0.019
P26	0.017
P27	0.015
P28	0.021
P29	0.025
P30	0.028
F01	0.0075
F02	0.011
F03	0.012
F04	0.0055
F05	0.0091
F06	0.0088

8.2. Filters transmittance curves

Dark Amber 022 LEE

204 Full C.T. Orange

205 Half C.T. Orange

106 Primary Red

8.3. Standards guidance for outdoor illumination

The below tables illustrate the applicable categories and recommended illumination strength and quality.

Zone	Lighting Environment	Example
E0	Substantially Dark	Natura 2000, UNESCO Starlight Reserve, IDA Dark Sky Park, Big astronomical observatories
E1	Dark	Relatively uninhabited rural areas
E2	Low light level	Sparsely populated rural areas
E3	Medium high light level	Well inhabited rural area and urban area
E4	High light level	Urban and city center and other commercial areas

NOTE Regardless of the level of urbanization, the recommendations for environmental zone E1 or E0 should be followed for all locations within 100 km of a major astronomical observatory. Regardless of the level of urbanization, at least the recommendations for environmental zone E2 should be followed for locations within 30 km of an active urban astronomical observatory, and for locations between 100 km and 300 km from a large optical astronomical observatory.

Table. The environmental zones of ambient light. Translated from the Swedish Standards by Authors. Main source: TRVINFRA-00396 Krav Version 1.0. Page 422.

The guideline values for lighting levels available from the Swedish Transport Administration for pedestrian and cycle paths are given in Table 13.1.3.1.3-1 P-class.

Classes	Horizontal Illuminance		Vision-impairing glare
	\bar{E}_i i lx (Maintained) ^a	E_{min} i lx (Maintained)	fTI i % (Maximum) ^b
P1	15,0	3,00	20
P2	10,0	2,00	25
P3	7,50	1,50	25
P4	5,00	1,00	30
P5	3,00	0,60	30
P6	2,00	0,40	35

P7	Performance not determined	Performance not determined	Performance not determined
----	----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------------

a to achieve uniformity, the current operating value of the average illuminance must not exceed 1.5 times the \bar{E} value for the specified class.
At an average illuminance higher than 15 lx, uniformity U_0 must be $\geq 1/3$.
b Regarding additional requirements when facial recognition is required.

Table. table of P-Classes translated by Authors. Main source: TRVINFRA-00396 Krav Version 1.0.

Vertical Illuminance	
Class	$E_{v,min}$ i lx [operating value]
EV1	50,0
EV2	30,0
EV3	10,0
EV4	7,50
EV5	5,00
EV6	0,50

Table. table EV Class for vertical flat surfaces translated by Authors. Main source: TRVINFRA-00396 Krav Version 1.0

Table 3. Lighting classes for pedestrian and low speed traffic areas as recommended in CIE 115: 2010.⁶

Lighting Class	Average horizontal illuminance (lux)	Minimum horizontal illuminance (lux)	Additional requirement if facial recognition is necessary.	
			Minimum vertical illuminance (lux)	Minimum semi-cylindrical illuminance (lux)
P1	15	3.0	5.0	3.0
P2	10	2.0	3.0	2.0
P3	7.5	1.5	2.5	1.5
P4	5.0	1.0	1.5	1.0
P5	3.0	0.6	1.0	0.6
P6	2.0	0.4	0.6	0.4

Standard (S)	Class	Average h illum (lux)	Min h illum (lux)	<i>fTI</i> % maximum (b)	Min V illum (lux)	Min semi-cylind. illum (lux)
CIE	P6	2	0.4	?	0.6	0.4
Norwegian	P6	2	0.4	35	0.6	0.2
Sweden	P6	2	0.4	35 ^b	(0.50) ^x	-

Notes:

a – Sweden, 1 – Norway: To achieve uniformity, the current operating value of the average illuminance must not exceed 1.5 times the *E* value for the specified class.

b – For Swedish when facial recognition is required.

x – Today in separate table to be used if required.

8.4. Characteristics of Lenses

LEDiL[®]

**PRODUCT
DATASHEET**
CA14392_LXP2-O-WAS

LXP2-O-WAS

Asymmetric beam for wall-washing and optimized for CREE XP-E. 14.6 mm high assembly with installation tape.

SPECIFICATION:

Dimensions	Ø 21.6
Height	14.6 mm
Fastening	tape
ROHS compliant	yes ⓘ

MATERIALS:

Component	Type	Material	Colour	Finish	Length (mm)
LXP2-O-WAS	Single lens	PMMA	clear		
LXP2-WAS-HLD	Holder	PC	black		
HEIDI-TAPE	Tape	Acrylic foam	black		

ORDERING INFORMATION:

Component	Qty in box	MOQ	MPQ	Box weight (kg)
CA14392_LXP2-O-WAS » Box size: 480 x 280 x 300 mm	1680	336	112	9.2

OPTICAL RESULTS (MEASURED):

<p>CREE LEDS</p> <p>LED XP-E2 FWHM / FWTM Asymmetric Efficiency 84 % Peak intensity 4 cd/Im LEDs/each optic 1 Light colour/type White Required components:</p>	<p>Light distribution files</p>	
<p>CREE LEDS</p> <p>LED XP-L HD FWHM / FWTM Asymmetric Efficiency 81 % Peak intensity 2.9 cd/Im LEDs/each optic 1 Light colour/type White Required components:</p>		<p>Light distribution files</p>

OPTICAL RESULTS (SIMULATED):

CREE
LEDs

LED	XP-G2
FWHM / FWTM	Asymmetric
Efficiency	74 %
Peak intensity	3.8 cd/m
LEDs/each optic	1
Light colour/type	White
Required components:	

Light distribution files

CREE
LEDs

LED	XP-G3
FWHM / FWTM	Asymmetric
Efficiency	82 %
Peak intensity	3.2 cd/m
LEDs/each optic	1
Light colour/type	White
Required components:	

Light distribution files

LUMINUS

LED	SST-20 Gen2
FWHM / FWTM	42.0 + 13.0° / 65.0 + 30.0°
Efficiency	89 %
Peak intensity	4.1 cd/m
LEDs/each optic	1
Light colour/type	White
Required components:	

Light distribution files

OPTICAL RESULTS (SIMULATED):

OPTICAL RESULTS (SIMULATED):

SAMSUNG

LED	LM301B
FWHM / FWTM	Asymmetric
Efficiency	75 %
Peak intensity	3.8 cd/m
LEDs/each optic	1
Light colour/type	White
Required components:	

Light distribution files

LED	Z5
FWHM / FWTM	Asymmetric
Efficiency	90 %
Peak intensity	4.2 cd/m
LEDs/each optic	1
Light colour/type	White
Required components:	

Light distribution files

